

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AKINTUNDE****FIRST NAME: TEMITOPE****PROGRAM CODE : DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: less than 5%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. There are many types of essays, but which will be discussed?
 - But we will discuss essays intended for Academic purposes in this Chapter.¹**
 - And we will examine all types of essays now.
 - And we will discuss only the important kinds of essays.
 - But we are examining only how to write articles in this chapter.

2. Academic or scholarly writing is...
 - Nonfictional paper is produced as part of Academic work.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021) 7.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

- Writing a Resume or CV.
 - Fictional writing of imaginary stories.
 - An essay competition.
3. What happened in the year 1937 according to the Turabian Rule of Style?
- The year Kate Turabian first assembled a set of guidelines for Student Writers at the University of Chicago.**³
 - The year the Television was invented.
 - The year of the first computer
 - When Kate Turabian died
4. What happens when a writer can explain the significance of research?
- He enters a conversation with the readers.**⁴
 - The readers are disappointed.
 - He enters contention with the readers.
 - His work has become boring.
5. One of the reasons for citing sources is...
- To give credit.**⁵
 - To share the sales income with the source.
 - To learn more things.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 14.

- So, the source can be a co-author.
6. Choice of Research Approach is directly tied to...
- Research problem and purpose.**⁶
 - Research Title.
 - Fictional writing of imaginary stories.
 - An essay competition³
7. A completed proposal is...
- When you present and justify your research idea to gain approval.**⁷
 - When you finish writing a thesis
 - When you pick the topic.
8. The Internet is often chosen to collect information because...
- The ease with which researchers can gain access.**⁸

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 21.

⁵ Ibid., 139.

⁶ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 135.

⁷ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 202.

⁸ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 462.

⁹ European Union, *English Style Guide* (Brussels: European Union, 2021), 48.

- It is cheaper than a physical library.
- The Internet is the surest source of information.

9. Foreign words and phrases used in an English text should be...

- Italicized.**⁹
- Bolded
- Underlined

10. The European Union, in geographical terms, consists of...

- The combined territory of member states**¹⁰
- All of Europe
- Europe and all English-speaking countries
- Europe and all French-speaking countries

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.
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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.